

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data validation

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Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data validation

About this document

This document is part of a webinar series organized by the Genesys team in 2023 on passport data preparation for publication in Genesys. The series covers practical approaches to data cleaning, standardization to MCPD v.2.1, validation, and eventual publication in Genesys, with a particular focus on genebanks managing passport data in spreadsheets such as Microsoft Excel.

This publication accompanies Part 3 of the series, which demonstrated practical approaches for identifying and correcting common data issues and validating taxonomic and geographic information prior to publication in Genesys.

This guidance is intended as a practical, step-by-step resource that participants can follow alongside the webinar recording or apply directly to their own datasets.

Webinar resources

Webinar recording:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RKXwq9Rt8HI>

Related documents in this series:

Part 1 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data cleaning

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/ak2d6y1hu9za4e830924r7508motvm49>

Part 2 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data standardization

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/zabludc6it46q2vwmufx4uxxtp9hksvh>

For questions, support, or to request the sample data file used during the training sessions, please contact: helpdesk@genesys-pgr.org

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data validation

After applying these steps you will be able to prepare your data for audits or online uploads.

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Mapping to MCPD: Formatting various data types

this section a continuation of the guidance on data standardizing

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20- Country of origin formatting to ISO 3166

The purpose of this step is to countries referenced in your passport data to their corresponding ISO 3166 code. This applies to the following passport data descriptors:

- Country of origin of collection or breeding (**ORIGCTY**)

Link to source database:

<https://github.com/lukes/ISO-3166-Countries-with-Regional-Codes/blob/master/all/all.csv>

In our previous documentation on data standardization, found in: <https://cropptrust.box.com/s/zabludc6it46q2vwmufx4uxxtp9hksvh>, in page 10, we showed how you can create a lookup table of country names to use in **ORIGCTY**.

Use that table to map country names their matching ISO code, either by:

- using the VLOOKUP function

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/vlookup-function-0bbc8083-26fe-4963-8ab8-93a18ad188a1>

- using the XLOOKUP function

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/xlookup-function-b7fd680e-6d10-43e6-84f9-88eae8bf5929>

- using Find and Replace

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/find-or-replace-text-and-numbers-on-a-worksheet-0e304ca5-ecef-4808-b90f-fdb42f892e90>

We recommend that you keep a copy of your original data stored in a safe location. This is important to run quality checks at a later stage. So don't forget to copy your original sheet to a new file before mapping to MCPD.

The VLOOKUP function is instead:

- BUSCARV in Spanish
- RECHERCHEV in French

The XLOOKUP function is the same both in Spanish and French

21- Codes of institutes formatting to WIEWS

The purpose of this step is to map institutes and other genebanks referenced in your passport data to their corresponding WIEWS code. This applies to the following passport data descriptors:

- Collecting institute code (**COLLCODE**)
- Breeding institute code (**BREDCODE**)
- Donor institute code (**DONORCODE**)
- Location of safety duplicates (**DUPLSITE**)

Link to WIEWS database: <https://www.fao.org/wiews/data/organizations/en/>

In our previous documentation on data standardization, found in: <https://croptrust.box.com/s/zabludc6it46q2vwmufx4uxxtp9hksvh>, in page 10, we showed how you can create a lookup table of WIEWS codes to map the passport data descriptors listed above.

Use that table to map institute names or acronyms to their matching WIEWS code, either by:

- using the VLOOKUP function
<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/vlookup-function-0bbc8083-26fe-4963-8ab8-93a18ad188a1>
- using the XLOOKUP function
<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/xlookup-function-b7fd680e-6d10-43e6-84f9-88eae8bf5929>
- using Find and Replace
<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/find-or-replace-text-and-numbers-on-a-worksheet-0e304ca5-ecef-4808-b90f-fdb42f892e90>

We recommend that you keep a copy of your original data stored in a safe location. This is important to run quality checks at a later stage. So don't forget to copy your original sheet to a new file before mapping to MCPD.

The VLOOKUP function is instead:

- BUSCARV in Spanish
- RECHERCHEV in French

The XLOOKUP function is the same both in Spanish and French

22- Multiple entries formatting

The format standard for multiple entries according to the MCPD standard is that the two coded values should be separated by a semicolon ; without space, for example for the STORAGE column, a multiple value would be **10;20**

The passport data descriptors that allow multiple entries in MCPD are the following:

- Collecting institute code (**COLLCODE**)
- Collecting institute name (**COLLNAME**)
- Collecting institute address (**COLLINSTADDRESS**)
- Accession name (**ACCENAME**)
- Breeding institute code (**BREDCODE**)
- Breeding institute name (**BREDNAME**)
- Location of safety duplicates (**DUPLSITE**)
- Institute of safety duplicates (**DUPLINSTNAME**)
- Type of germplasm storage (**STORAGE**)

The formula to use to merge to entries seperated by ; is:

=J2&";"&K2

J	K	L
Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2	DUPLSITE
NGA039	NOR051	=J2&";"&K2
NGA040	NOR052	
NGA041	NOR053	
NGA042	NOR054	
NGA043	NOR055	
NGA044	NOR056	
NGA045	NOR057	
NGA046	NOR058	
NGA047	NOR059	
NGA048	NOR060	
NGA049	NOR061	
NGA050	NOR062	
NGA051	NOR063	
NGA052	NOR064	
NGA053	NOR065	

DUPLSITE
NGA039;NOR051
NGA040;NOR052
NGA041;NOR053
NGA042;NOR054
NGA043;NOR055
NGA044;NOR056
NGA045;NOR057
NGA046;NOR058
NGA047;NOR059
NGA048;NOR060
NGA049;NOR061
NGA050;NOR062
NGA051;NOR063
NGA052;NOR064
NGA053;NOR065

23- Missing values or blank cells formatting

The purpose of this step is to replace blank values with N.A or NULL, or vice versa: replace NULL or N.A with a blank, depending on your genebank's standard.

For uploading data in Genesys, please make sure that blank or missing values are kept as blank cells.

In order to replace N.A or NULL entries with blanks, you may use the Find and Replace tool:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/find-or-replace-text-and-numbers-on-a-worksheet-0e304ca5-ecef-4808-b90f-fdb42f892e90>

In order to do the opposite: replace blank values with NULL or N.A, you first need to select the blank values in your table by selecting all the table, then in the Home ribbon, click on Find and Select menu, and selecting Go to special sub-menu item:

1

2

3

4

5

	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
1	Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2	DUPLSITE	ORIGCTY	DECLATITL	DECLONGITL	STORAGE	REMARKS
2	NOR051	NGA039;NOR051	Zambia	13.1404	27.8465		10	
3	NOR052	NGA040;NOR052	Zambia	13.1404	28.8465		11	
4	NOR053	NGA041;NOR053	Zambia	13.1404	29.8465		12	
5	NOR054	NGA042;NOR054	Zambia	13.1404	30.8465		13	
6	NOR055	NGA043;NOR055	Zambia	13.1404	31.8465		14	
7	NOR056	NGA044;NOR056	Zambia	13.1404	32.8465		15	
8	NOR057	NGA045;NOR057	Zambia	13.1404	33.8465		16	
9	NOR058	NGA046;NOR058	Peru	13.1404	34.8465		17	
10	NOR059	NGA047;NOR059	Peru	13.1404	35.8465		18	
11	NOR060	NGA048;NOR060	Peru	13.1404	36.8465		19	
12	NOR061	NGA049;NOR061	Peru	13.1404	37.8465		20	
13	NOR062	NGA050;NOR062	Zambia	13.1404	38.8465		21	
14	NOR063	NGA051;NOR063	Zambia	13.1404	39.8465		22	
15	NOR064	NGA052;NOR064	Zambia	13.1404	40.8465		23	
16	NOR065	NGA053;NOR065	Zambia	13.1404	41.8465			
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								
22								

24- Validating the click-and-drag error

Excel's click-and-drag functionality, also known as "Fill Handle", is the plus (+) icon that appears when moving the mouse or cursor to the right bottom of the selected cell. Using this plus icon, we can pull the active cells formatting, series, or any pattern, to the left, right, top, or bottom.

For example, look at the below image to see what the Fill Handle looks like:

Click-and-drag helps us fill continuous cells with a series, pattern, or dates to a single row and column at a time. It is also used to copy a formula or data point in one cell for the rest of the column to avoid copy-pasting.

Sometimes, clicking and dragging a cell prompts Excel to copy this cell to the rest of the column, while other times, the same option prompts Excel to continue the pattern, for example dragging a cell that contains **1**, will populate the rest of the cells with **2**, then **3**, then **4**, etc.

This can lead to errors in your passport data such as dates, geographic coordinates, or coded values where you meant to click-and-drag to copy the cell, but instead Excel continues the number as a pattern by adding an increment of 1 or 10.

A simple way to check if this error is present in your dates, geographic coordinates or coded columns is by calculating the difference between consecutive cells.

25- Checking for duplicated accession numbers and rows

Checking for duplicated accession numbers

Select all data in the column Accession number (**ACCENUMB**), then in the Home ribbon, click on Conditional Formatting menu, then select the Highlight Cell Rules sub-menu item. From there select Duplicated Values option:

From this dialog box, select the format you would like Excel to highlight duplicated values with, then click OK.

The screenshot shows the Excel spreadsheet with the 'ACCENUMB' column highlighted in red. A hand cursor points to the highlighted cells, which are circled with a yellow circle containing the number '5'.

INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT
The Shire National Genebank	OS-102	Oryza	sativa	20191210	21	10
The Shire National Genebank	OS-103	Oryza	sativa	20191211	61	10
The Shire National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	sativa	20191212	21	30
The Shire National Genebank	OS-105	Oryza	sativa	20191213	26	30
The Shire National Genebank	OS-106	Manihot	esculenttttt	20191214	40	40
The Shire National Genebank	OS-107	Manihot	esculenta	20191215	23	30
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	esculenta	20191216	26	50
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Solanum	lycopersicum	20191217	26	50
The Shire National Genebank	OS-107	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191218	26	50
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191219	26	50
The Shire National Genebank	OS-109	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191220	23	30
The Shire National Genebank	OS-110	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191221	40	40
The Shire National Genebank	OS-111	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191222	40	40
The Shire National Genebank	OS-112	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191223	40	40
The Shire National Genebank	OS-112	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191224	40	40

25- Checking for duplicated accession numbers and rows

You may now filter those duplicated accessions in your table by clicking on the filter icon next to the **ACCENUMB** column title, and selecting Filter by colour:

INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPST
The Shire National Genebank	OS-102			20191210	21	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-103			20191211	61	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-104			20191212	21	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-105			20191213	26	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-106			20191214	40	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-107			20191215	23	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108			20191216	26	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108			20191217	26	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-107			20191218	26	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-108			20191219	26	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-109			20191220	23	
The Shire National Genebank	OS-110					
The Shire National Genebank	OS-111					
The Shire National Genebank	OS-112					
The Shire National Genebank	OS-112					

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC
7	The Shire National Genebank	OS-107	Manihot	esculenta	20191215	23
8	The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	esculenta	20191216	26
9	The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Solanum	lycopersicum	20191217	26
10	The Shire National Genebank	OS-107	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191218	26
11	The Shire National Genebank	OS-108	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191219	26
15	The Shire National Genebank	OS-112	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191223	40
16	The Shire National Genebank	OS-112	Slanum	lycopersicum	20191224	40
17						

We encourage you consult with other colleagues or managers at the genebank in order to decide if/how to fix these occurrences of duplicated accession numbers.

Keep in mind to modify not only you internal database, but also the labels of the accessions and all related material in the genebank, as well as updating any public databases or registries such as DOI, FAO WIEWS, Genesys, SGSV portal when you modify any accession number.

25- Checking for duplicated accession numbers and rows

Checking for duplicated rows

The purpose of this step is to check if entire rows are duplicated in your dataset based on a comparison of specific passport data descriptors of your choosing.

In the table below for example, you can decide that the cut-off to decide if a row is the same is if the accession number (ACCENUMB), genus name (GENUS) and species name (SPECIES) are the same.

In this case you can create a new column that combines ACCENUMB, GENUS and SPECIES and apply the conditional formatting to it.

After you create a new column, apply this formula in the example below:

=B2&C2&D2

SUM | =B2&C2&D2

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	Column1	ACQDATE	COLLSRC
2	The Shire National Genebank	OS-102	Oryza	sativa	=B2&C2&D2	20191210	21
3	The Shire National Genebank	OS-103	Oryza	sativa		20191211	61
4	The Shire National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	sativa		20191212	21
5	The Shire National Genebank	OS-105	Oryza	sativa		20191213	26
6	The Shire National Genebank	OS-106	Manihot	esculentttt		20191214	40

↓

Then select this new column and apply to it the same Conditional Formatting as described in page 8.

This will highlight the rows that have the same accession number and genus and species names.

You can filter these occurrences following the steps described in page 9.

Column1
OS-102Oryzasativa
OS-103Oryzasativa
OS-104Oryzasativa
OS-105Oryzasativa
OS-106Manihotesculentttt
OS-107Manihotesculenta
OS-108Manihotesculenta
OS-108Solanumlycopersicum
OS-107Slanumlycopersicum
OS-108Slanumlycopersicum
OS-109Slanumlycopersicum
OS-110Slanumlycopersicum
OS-111Slanumlycopersicum
OS-112Slanumlycopersicum
OS-112Slanumlycopersicum

You can clear the format of conditional formatting by clicking on the Home Ribbon, the Clear menu (eraser icon), then select Clear Formats.

26- Validating taxonomy

This step covers the following taxonomy columns:

- Genus names (**GENUS**)
- Species names (**SPECIES**)
- Species authority names (**SPAUTHOR**)
- Subtaxon names (**SUBTAXA**)
- Subtaxon authority (**SUBTAUTHOR**)

To check for misspellings in the taxonomy, or to auto-complete your taxonomy with species or subtaxon authority names according to GRIN, you can use the Genesys Validator Tool:

<https://validator.genesys-pgr.org/>

In order for the Genesys Validator Tool to work, you need to have the column titles in MCPD (for example your genus name column should be titled GENUS).

Select all the taxonomy columns you want to validate, and paste them in the rectangle in the validator tool's page:

GENUS	SPECIES	ACC
Oryza	sativa	201:
Manihot	esculenta	201:
Manihot	esculenta	201:
Manihot	esculenta	201:

Submit data for validation

1. Copy-paste data from Excel:

Select the range of cells (including headers) in Excel and paste the data in to the textbox.

```
GENUS  SPECIES
Oryza  sativa
Oryza  sativa
Oryza  sativa
Oryza  sativa
Manihot esculenta
Manihot esculenta
```

After pasting the taxonomy data in the validator tool, click on **Validate Taxonomic data** button at the end of the page:

Flag non-current taxa:

Yes No

4. Preview or Download

Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Validate Taxonomic data

Validate Country of Origin

Classify Land or Water

26- Validating taxonomy

The tool will return your data with additional columns in **yellow** that include the validation and a paragraph on how to interpret the results in the columns in yellow:

Notice that even though the original taxonomic data provided in this sample does not include the species authority (SPAUTHOR), the validator tool returned it. This demonstrates how you can complete your data by using this tool.

How to interpret results?

"_parsed" columns

For numeric values these columns contain the value as parsed by the program. See if setting a different decimal mark character helps.

"_check" and "_distance" columns

Columns highlighted Yellow were injected into your dataset at most appropriate positions. They contain the results of the validation run

- **OK** means that a 100% match was found in the taxonomic databases, the data is valid.
- **blank (empty) cell** means the system could not find a decent match in the taxonomic databases and offers no suggestion.

"_distance" columns

"ORIGCTY_distance" column contains distance between lat/lon to the nearest point on the border of the specified country.

"_fix" columns

"DECLATITUDE_fix" and "DECLONGITUDE_fix" columns contain adjusted coordinates (flipped, swapped) that fall within specified "ORIG

Results

GENUS	GENUS_check	SPECIES	SPAUTHOR_check	SPECIES_check	GRINTAX_speciesId	GRINTAX_speciesCurrent
Oryza	OK	sativa	L.	OK	26077	true
Oryza	OK	sativa	L.	OK	26077	true
Oryza	OK	sativa	L.	OK	26077	true
Oryza	OK	sativa	L.	OK	26077	true
Manihot	OK	esculenta	Crantz	OK	431678	true
Manihot	OK	esculenta	Crantz	OK	431678	true
Manihot	OK	esculenta	Crantz	OK	431678	true

You can download the results as a CSV file, by ticking the box "Download results as CSV" in step 4 of the Validator Tool:

Flag non-current taxa:

Yes No

4. Preview or Download

Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Validate Taxonomic data

Validate Country of Origin

Classify Land or Water

Or you can copy the results page and directly paste it in Excel.

Please note that the results of this tool are based on the GRIN taxonomy. Before applying any changes to your data based on these results, please consult with colleagues and managers at your genebank, as these are only suggestions.

27- Validating country of origin

This step covers the following geography columns:

- Country of origin (**ORIGCTY**)
- Decimal Latitude (**DECLATITUDE**)
- Decimal Longitude (**DECLONGITUDE**)

To check for misspellings in the codes of countries of origin, or to auto-complete your geographic data with the codes of countries of origin based on the latitude and longitude, you can use the Genesys Validator Tool:

<https://validator.genesys-pgr.org/>

In order for the Genesys Validator Tool to work, you need to have the column titles in MCPD (for example your decimal latitude column name should be titled **DECLATITUDE**). The column entries should also comply with the MCPD standard for the validator tool to work, eg. Zambia should be written as **ZMB**)

Select all the geography columns you want to validate, and paste them in the rectangle in the validator tool's page:

ORIGCTY	DECLATITUDE	DECLONGITUDE
Zambia	13.1404	27.8465
Zambia	13.1404	28.8465
Zambia	13.1404	29.8465
Zambia	13.1404	30.8465
Zambia	13.1404	31.8465
Zambia	13.1404	32.8465
Zambia	13.1404	33.8465
Peru	13.1404	34.8465

Submit data for validation

1. Copy-paste data from Excel

Select the range of cells (including headers) in Excel and paste the data in to the textbox.

ORIGCTY	DECLATITUDE	DECLONGITUDE
Zambia	13.1404	27.8465
Zambia	13.1404	28.8465
Zambia	13.1404	29.8465
Zambia	13.1404	30.8465
Zambia	13.1404	31.8465
Zambia	13.1404	32.8465

After pasting the geographic data in the validator tool, click on **Validate Country of origin** button at the end of the page:

Flag non-current taxa:

Yes No

4. Preview or Download

Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Validate Taxonomic data

Validate Country of Origin

Classify Land or Water

27- Validating country of origin

The tool will return your data with additional columns in **yellow** that include the validation and a paragraph on how to interpret the results in the columns in yellow:

How to interpret results?

"_parsed" columns

For numeric values these columns contain the value as parsed by the program. See if setting a different decimal mark character helps.

"_check" and "_distance" columns

Columns highlighted Yellow were injected into your dataset at most appropriate positions. They contain the results of the validation run.

- **OK** means that a 100% match was found in the taxonomic databases, the data is valid.
- *blank (empty) cell* means the system could not find a decent match in the taxonomic databases and offers no suggestion.

"_distance" columns

"ORIGCTY_distance" column contains distance between lat/lon to the nearest point on the border of the specified country.

"_fix" columns

"DECLATITUDE_fix" and "DECLONGITUDE_fix" columns contain adjusted coordinates (flipped, swapped) that fall within specified "ORIGCTY".

ORIGCTY_original2	ORIGCTY	ORIGCTY_check	ORIGCTY_distance	DECLATITUDE	DECLATITUDE_parsed	DECLATITUDE_fix	DECLONGITUDE	DECLONGITUDE_fix
Zambia	(a) ZMB	SDN ✓	2381032	13.1404 ✓	13.14039993	13.14039993	27.8465 ✓	27.8465
Zambia	ZMB	SDN	2368591	13.1404	13.14039993	-13.14039993	28.8465	28.8465
Zambia	(b) ZMB ✓	SDN ✗	2361268	13.1404	13.14039993	-13.14039993 ✓	29.8465	29.8465
Zambia	ZMB	SDN	2359110	13.1404	13.14039993	-13.14039993	30.8465	30.8465
Zambia	ZMB	SDN	2362132	13.1404	13.14039993	-13.14039993	31.8465	31.8465

You can download the results as a CSV file, by ticking the box "Download results as CSV" in step 4 of the Validator Tool:

Flag non-current taxa:
 Yes No

4. Preview or Download
 Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Validate Taxonomic data Validate Country of Origin Classify Land or Water

Or you can copy the results page and directly paste it in Excel.

It is important to **either** accept the validator's suggestion of ORIGCTY_check (example a) **or** the suggestion for both DECLATITUDE_check and DECLONGITUDE_check (example b).

Please do not cherry pick the results and consult with colleagues or managers before applying these changes.

28- Validating land or water

This step covers the following geography columns:

- Decimal Latitude (**DECLATITUDE**)
- Decimal Longitude (**DECLONGITUDE**)

To check if the geographic coordinates of an accession fall on land or in sea water, lakes, or rivers, you can use the Genesys Validator Tool:

<https://validator.genesys-pgr.org/>

 In order for the Genesys Validator Tool to work, you need to have the column titles in MCPD (for example your decimal latitude column name should be titled **DECLATITUDE**). The column entries should also comply with the MCPD standard for the validator tool to work, eg. Zambia should be written as **ZMB**)

Select all the geography columns you want to validate, and paste them in the rectangle in the validator tool's page:

ORIGCTY	DECLATITUDE	DECLONGITUDE
Zambia	13.1404	27.8465
Zambia	13.1404	28.8465
Zambia	13.1404	29.8465
Zambia	13.1404	30.8465
Zambia	13.1404	31.8465
Zambia	13.1404	32.8465
Zambia	13.1404	33.8465
Peru	13.1404	34.8465

Submit data for validation

1. Copy-paste data from Excel

Select the range of cells (including headers) in Excel and paste the data in to the textbox.

ORIGCTY	DECLATITUDE	DECLONGITUDE
Zambia	13.1404	27.8465
Zambia	13.1404	28.8465
Zambia	13.1404	29.8465
Zambia	13.1404	30.8465
Zambia	13.1404	31.8465
Zambia	13.1404	32.8465

After pasting the geographic data in the validator tool, click on **Classify land or water** button at the end of the page:

Flag non-current taxa:

Yes No

4. Preview or Download

Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Validate Taxonomic data

Validate Country of Origin

Classify Land or Water

28- Validating land or water

The tool will return your data with additional columns in **yellow** that include the validation and a paragraph on how to interpret the results in the columns in yellow:

How to interpret results?

"_parsed" columns

For numeric values these columns contain the value as parsed by the program. See if setting a different decimal mark character helps.

"_check" and "_distance" columns

Columns highlighted Yellow were injected into your dataset at most appropriate positions. They contain the results of the validation run.

- **OK** means that a 100% match was found in the taxonomic databases, the data is valid.
- *blank (empty) cell* means the system could not find a decent match in the taxonomic databases and offers no suggestion.

"_distance" columns

"ORIGCTY_distance" column contains distance between lat/lon to the nearest point on the border of the specified country.

"_fix" columns

"DECLATITUDE_fix" and "DECLONGITUDE_fix" columns contain adjusted coordinates (flipped, swapped) that fall within specified "ORIGCTY".

Results

ORIGCTY	DECLATITUDE	DECLATITUDE_parsed	DECLONGITUDE	DECLONGITUDE_parsed	LANDorSEA_check
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	27.8465	27.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	28.8465	28.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	29.8465	29.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	30.8465	30.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	31.8465	31.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	32.8465	32.84650040	Land
Zambia	13.1404	13.14039993	33.8465	33.84650040	Land
Peru	13.1404	13.14039993	34.8465	34.84650040	Land
Peru	13.1404	13.14039993	35.8465	35.84650040	Land

You can download the results as a CSV file, by ticking the box "Download results as CSV" in step 4 of the Validator Tool:

Flag non-current taxa:
 Yes No

4. Preview or Download
Tick the box if you want to download results as CSV file. Leave unticked to see results in the browser.

Download results as CSV

Or you can copy the results page and directly paste it in Excel.

The results are found in **LANDorSEA_check** yellow column.

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